

PB_4 will reset sequencer, but only stops it while the button is held. After releasing it, sequencer continues to run if it was running before.

PB_5 will stop the sequencer and then start to iterate it everytime repressed for one step. Not sure if it first stops to the current step and then next press will iterate. Or if it stops and iterates on the first press already.

PB_6 same as PB_GREEN.

R4 is combined resistance of two resistors in series. Could be that the idea was to have on resistor for buttons, and one for the four jacks. But accidentally on the bridge they were hooked together. Not that it matters really...

BLUE jack is connected to the beginning of the shift buffer (SR).

HIGH on RED jack will reset the sequencer, but will not stop it.

GREEN PB starts sequencer if it was not running.

WHITE PB will reset and stop sequencer if it was running.

After RESET, through either PB or jack: SR1 will be HIGH, SR2[10] all LOW. Counter A all ports LOW. Counter B all bits LOW.

Counter A all ports will switch to HIGH when sequencer is started and it iterates for the first time (SR1 => LOW, SR2 => HIGH).

Counter B is positioned as SR11, so it will iterate on next tick when SR10 is HIGH (but it iterates on rising edge so it needs to see LOW state before advancing).

Counter B could be more useful, would it have inverter on the outputs. Then it would after reset be 11111, then overflow to 0 and start counting up LSB on the left.

Unused banana jacks.

Main power input DB-9 socket according original documentation. CONFIRM this!

Decent drum sound only from channel 3. Might be something broken on other channels 1 and 2. However the circuit differs between these channels, might be problem in the design itself.

DSW PCB is missing. Only digital chips, would be easy to reconstruct using either MRTL (even made from transistors) or even CMOS chips (3.6V logic levels). Atmega uC would also work here.

According schematic draft, SW input will enable either S or S₁ input. Essentially this is digitally controlled SPDT switch / relay.

